

ISic0211

I.Sicily inscription 0211

Language

Latin

Type

funerary

Material

limestone

Object

stele

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Thermae Himeraeae

Place of origin (modern)

Termini Imerese

Provenance

Necropolis di S.Antonino

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Termini Imerese, Museo Civico
Baldassare Romano, inventory 61

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. L(ucius) · Pub[li]([icius])

2. Iucund(us)

Apparatus

Text of ILTermini and photograph

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 175692

EDR 077922

EDCS 8900400

Bibliography

1888-. L'année épigraphique: revue des publications épigraphiques relatives a l'antiquité romaine.. *L'année épigraphique : revue des publications épigraphiques relatives a l'antiquité romaine..* At 1980.0522

Bivona, L. 1994. Iscrizioni latine lapidarie del museo civico di Termini Imerese. *Kokalos Supplementi / Sikelika serie storica*. Palermo / Rome. At 134

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